

1 **Microbial conversion of carbon dioxide and** 2 **hydrogen into the fine chemicals hydroxyectoine** 3 **and ectoine**

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10

11 **Abstract**

12 This study explores a novel conversion of CO₂ into the chemicals hydroxyectoine and ectoine
13 which have high retail values in the pharmaceutical industry. Firstly, 11 species of microbes able
14 to use CO₂ and H₂ and that have the genes for ectoines synthesis (*ectABCD*) were identified
15 through genomic mining. Laboratory validation was then conducted to verify the species that had
16 the capacity to produce ectoines from CO₂. These analyses showed that the most promising
17 bacteria for this bioconversion were *Hydrogenovibrio marinus*, *Rhodococcus opacus*, and
18 *Hydrogenibacillus schlegelii*. Upon salinity and H₂/CO₂/O₂ ratio optimization, *H. marinus*
19 accumulated 85 mg of ectoine g biomass⁻¹. Interestingly, *R. opacus* and *H. schlegelii* mainly

20 produced hydroxyectoine (53 and 62 mg g biomass⁻¹) which has a higher commercial value.

21 Overall, these results constituted the first proof of a novel valorization platform of CO₂ and laid

22 the foundation for a new economic niche aimed at CO₂ recircularization into pharmaceuticals.

23

24 1. Introduction

25 The utilization of carbon dioxide (CO₂) as a carbon block for the synthesis of valuable chemicals
26 and fuels is of increasing interest (Kumar et al., 2018). CO₂ emissions represent the biggest fraction
27 (78.8 %, data from 2021) of the total emitted greenhouse gases (GHG) worldwide (EEA (European
28 Environmental Agency), 2021; National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, NOAA, 2020).
29 A large part of these emissions is vented into the atmosphere by means of industrial processes.
30 Industrially produced CO₂ can be emitted in the form of highly concentrated flue gas streams (15–
31 80% CO₂), e.g. in industrial processes producing ammonia, ethanol, steel, and paper or in the form
32 of lower concentration emissions (8–10% CO₂), such as in natural gas-fired power plants or biogas
33 combustion (Kumar et al., 2018). In these scenarios, CO₂ is a perfect feedstock for in situ
34 transformation into chemicals using autotrophic organisms without light requirements (dark
35 fixation) (Nisar et al., 2021).

36 Current dark CO₂ fixation processes normally target relatively low value bulk chemicals, such
37 as alcohols, fatty acids, and organic acids, and are based on the application of a restricted number
38 of model organisms (Kumar et al., 2018). Thus, the expansion of both, the type of autotrophic
39 organisms used for CO₂ conversion, and the production of higher value chemicals (e.g. chemicals
40 for cosmetics and pharmaceuticals), is interesting to broaden the potential of dark CO₂ fixation
41 processes with application in diverse industries.

42 Interesting products, due to their high value, are those produced by extremophilic bacteria and
43 archaea that live at high salinity – specifically the extremolyte, ectoine, and its derivate,
44 hydroxyectoine (Becker and Wittmann, 2020; Widderich et al., 2016). Ectoine accounts for a retail
45 value of €1000 kg⁻¹ and has exceptional properties (protectors of cell membranes and tissues) and
46 is implemented in health-promoting and therapeutic activities (Liu et al., 2019). Hydroxyectoine,

47 due to its hydroxylated nature, confers additional protective properties against heat and dryness
48 and it has an even higher commercial value than ectoine (Liu et al., 2019). Both, ectoine and
49 hydroxyectoine (ectoines), are manufactured through bioprocesses using sugars. However, little
50 research has explored the possibility of the production of ectoines from renewable or waste-based
51 carbon sources (Cantera et al., 2018; Kunte et al., 2014). In fact, the transformation of CO₂ into
52 these compounds has never been experimentally assessed.

53 One of the main difficulties for the cost-effective microbial transformation of CO₂ is the
54 selection of a suitable, available energy source. Chemolithoautotrophs can use a variety of energy
55 sources – from metals and reduced sulfur and nitrogen compounds, to gaseous compounds such
56 as, CO or H₂ (Anand et al., 2020). Although the use of liquid waste streams containing any of the
57 potential electron donors can be of great interest from an economic point of view, manufacturing
58 products suitable for human-use requires a feedstock that is free of potential hazardous materials
59 (Kunte et al., 2014). In this regard, the use of clean gases as an energy source, such as H₂ or
60 impurity free pre-treated syngas, can be the best approach for the production of chemicals for
61 pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and medicines. Renewable H₂ can be produced via a number of
62 sustainable technologies, including biomass pyrolysis-gasification, biomass dark fermentation,
63 supercritical water gasification, and water electrolysis using renewable electricity (Bommareddy
64 et al., 2020).

65 Usually, the organisms implemented for the transformation of CO₂ and H₂ are anaerobic
66 chemolithoautotrophs, mainly acetogens, which suffer from energetic limitations with final low
67 productivities of the chemical (Katsyv and Müller, 2020). Conversely, aerobic
68 chemolithoautotrophs – microorganisms able to grow with CO₂ as the sole carbon source and H₂

69 as the energy source, in the presence of air – could become a cost-effective, sustainable, circular
70 and climate neutral novel platform for the production of pharmaceuticals.

71 To this aim, this research identified novel aerobic microbes able to produce ectoines from CO₂
72 and H₂. First, halophilic microbes able to use CO₂ and H₂ as the carbon or energy source were
73 determined based on literature and databases and their genomes downloaded and mined for the
74 genes involved in ectoine and hydroxyectoine synthesis pathways. The transformation of CO₂ into
75 ectoines was tested in the laboratory for proof-of-concept validation. The most promising bacteria,
76 according to their growth rates and (hydroxy)ectoine production, were implemented in batch
77 bioreactors and the process was optimized to obtain high (hydroxy)ectoine content linked to CO₂
78 removal.

79 **2. Materials and Methods**

80 *2.1. Selection of potential chemolithoautotrophic organisms able to produce ectoine*

81 Halophilic and halotolerant chemolithotrophs were identified from literature searches (see
82 supplementary material). Genomes of the identified species were downloaded from the National
83 Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI, Datasets v. 10.0.0; (see supplementary material))
84 and screened for genes encoding for enzymes involved in ectoines' synthesis pathways,
85 specifically: *ectA*, *ectB*, *ectC* and *ectD*. Moreover, the presence of *ectR*, an important
86 transcriptional regulator of this pathway, and two genes involved in the production of the precursor
87 L-2,4-diaminobutyrate (aspartate kinase: *ask* and aspartate semi-aldehyde dehydrogenase: *asd*),
88 were also assessed. Alignments or profile hidden-Markov models (HMM) for each gene were
89 retrieved from public databases (see supplementary material). HMMer 3.1b2 (<http://hmmer.org>)
90 was used to build profile HMMs of gene alignments, and to search all HMMs against the
91 downloaded proteomes. To corroborate the detection of gene orthologs, the protein sequences with

92 significant hits ($<1e^{-5}$) were retrieved and annotated using Interproscan v.5.36-75.0 (Jones et al.,
93 2014). First, protein sequences identified as EctB and EctC were selected if they yielded significant
94 ($<1e^{-5}$) Interproscan hits to TIGR00709 and PF06339, respectively. Protein sequences detected as
95 EctD and EctA were corroborated as such if they had significant Interproscan hits to PF05721 and
96 PF00583, respectively; sequences detected as EctR were selected if a Blastp search against the
97 COG database (Galperin et al., 2015) retrieved at least 5 significant ($<1e^{-5}$) best hits against
98 proteins classified as COG1846.

99 2.2. Source of microorganisms

100 All strains used in this study were purchased from DSMZ (Brunswick, Germany): *Alkalilimnicola*
101 *ehrllichii* (DSM 17681), *Hydrogenibacillus schlegelii* (DSM 2000), *Hydrogenovibrio marinus*
102 (DSM 11271), *Pseudonocardia autotrophica* (DSM 535), *Pseudonocardia carboxydivorans*
103 (DSM 43559), *Pseudonocardia dioxanivorans* (DSM 44775) and *Rhodococcus opacus* (DSM
104 43205). Physiological characteristics of these strains are included in Table S1. All cultures were
105 purchased as freeze dried biomass, except *H. marinus* that was purchased as an active growth
106 culture in medium (DSM 744). *H. schlegelii* was activated in medium DSM 260; all the other
107 freeze dried cultures were activated in trypticase soy broth (medium DSM 535). Inoculation from
108 freeze dried stocks was done in sealed serum bottles of 200 mL containing 100 mL of medium and
109 100 mL of air in the headspace at atmospheric pressure.

110 2.3. Mineral salt medium

111 Growth tests with H_2/CO_2 were performed using ammonium mineral salt medium (AMS). This
112 medium contained ($g L^{-1}$): $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ - 1.0, $CaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ - 0.11, NH_4Cl - 0.5, $FeSO_4 \cdot 7 H_2O$ -
113 0.005. Medium was supplemented with trace elements ($mg L^{-1}$): $CuCl_2$ - 0.01, $FeCl_2$ - 0.9, $ZnCl_2$
114 - 0.06, $NiCl_2$ - 0.01, $CoCl_2$ - 0.06, Na_2MoO_4 - 0.03, $MnCl_2$ - 0.06, H_3BO_3 - 0.06, Na_2SeO_3 - 0.4,

115 Na₂WO₄·0.01) and vitamins (mg L⁻¹): biotin - 0.02, nicotinamid - 0.2, p-aminobenzoic acid - 0.1,
116 thiamin - 0.2, panthotenic acid - 0.1, pyridoxamine - 0.5, cyanocobalamine - 0.1, riboflavine - 0.1.
117 NaCl was added to the AMS at different concentrations (from 30 to 100 g L⁻¹). Nitrate was added
118 as KNO₃⁻ at a final concentration of 620.0 mg NO₃⁻ L⁻¹. Nitrate was added to the AMS to avoid
119 nitrogen limitation during ectoine production and also to study its potential use as electron acceptor
120 when there was oxygen limitation. AMS was autoclaved at 1.5 atm and 121°C for 20 min. pH was
121 buffered around 7 by adding 15 mL L⁻¹ of sterile stock solution of 50.0 mL L⁻¹ of NaHCO₃ (1M),
122 5.0 mL L⁻¹ of Na₂CO₃ (1M) and 20.0 mL L⁻¹ of sterile stock solution of KH₂PO₄ (0.1M) and
123 Na₂HPO₄·12 H₂O (0.08M). Tests where CO₂ was monitored were not supplemented with
124 carbonate/bicarbonate buffer and initial pH was adjusted to 7 using a solution of NaOH 3M.

125 2.4. Analytical procedures

126 2.4.1 Ectoine, hydroxyectoine and nitrate determination

127 The intra-cellular ectoine and hydroxyectoine in 2 mL of cultivation broth was extracted following
128 the protocol described by Cantera et al. (2018). The concentration of ectoine was measured with a
129 Shimadzu Prominence-i LC-2030C plus HPLC (Shimadzu, Japan) with a UV detector at 210 nm.
130 HPLC was equipped with a Polaris, NH₂, 180Å, 3 µm, 4,6 x 150 mm (Agilent Technologies,
131 USA). The mobile phase was acetonitrile/H₂O 75/25 (%) at a flow rate of 0.6 mL min⁻¹. Oven
132 temperature was set at 30 °C. External standards of commercially available ectoine [(S)-b-2-
133 methyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro-pyrimidine-4-carboxylic acid, purity 95%] and hydroxyectoine [(4 S,5
134 S) – 5-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydropyrimidine-4-carboxylic acid, purity 95%] (Sigma
135 Aldrich, Germany) were used for quantification. The intra-cellular ectoine and hydroxyectoine
136 content were calculated according to Eq.1(1).

137
$$Ect/Hydro\ content = \frac{[Ect - Hydro]}{[X]}$$
 (1) ; where [Ect-Hydro] is the ectoine or hydroxyectoine
138 concentration and [X] is the biomass dry weight. For flocculating species (where non-
139 representative liquid sample could be withdrawn), the Ect-Hydro content was obtained by
140 collecting the total liquid of the bottles.

141 Nitrate from the supernatant was measured on a ICS-2100 (Thermo Scientific, USA) equipped
142 with an AS19 column, 2x250 mm (Thermo Scientific, USA). The mobile phase consisted of a
143 gradient of KOH, ranging from 1 – 40 mM KOH, generated by a cartridge and the flow was 0.4
144 mL min⁻¹. 30 µL of the supernatant were transferred to HPLC vials containing 970 µL of milli-Q
145 water. The peaks were detected using a suppressed conductivity detector.

146 *2.4.2 H₂ and CO₂ determination*

147 CO₂ and H₂ were measured with a Compact GC equipped with 2 lines, both with a TCD detector
148 (Interscience, The Netherlands). To measure CO₂ a RT-Q-bond column ,10 m x 0.32 mm (Restek,
149 USA) was used. The valve (injection) oven and the column oven were set at 100 °C, the TCD
150 detector temperature was 110 °C and the TCD filament temperature was 175 °C. The carrier gas
151 was Argon with an applied pressure of 80 kPa. For H₂, a Carboxen 1010 column ,3 m x 0.32 mm
152 (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) followed by a Molsieve 5A column,30m x 0.32 mm (Sigma-Aldrich, USA)
153 was used. The valve (injection), the column oven, the TCD detector temperature and the TCD
154 filament temperature were set at 100, 140, 110 and 175 °C, respectively. Argon was again the
155 carrier gas, here with an applied pressure of 325 kPa.

156 The CO₂ and H₂ consumption were calculated using Eq. (2).

157 (2) $Y_{CO_2/X} = \frac{-\Delta[CO_2]_{e-phase}}{\Delta[X]_{e-phase}}$; where $[CO_2]_{e-phase}$ is the variation in the content of CO_2 in the
158 headspace and liquid phase during exponential growth phase and $[X]_{e-phase}$ is the content of biomass
159 in the liquid phase during exponential growth phase.

160 The total CO_2 content (g) was calculated as the sum of CO_2 in the gas and aqueous phases. The
161 concentration ($g\ m^{-3}$) of CO_2 in the headspace at atmospheric pressure was determined with the
162 GC-TCD. The aqueous CO_2 concentration was estimated according to the dimensionless Henry
163 constant for CO_2 ($K_{Hcc}=1.22$ (gas phase/liquid phase)). The amount of H_2CO_3 and CO_3^- were
164 calculated using the Henderson-Hasselbach equation (Eq. 3):

165 (3) $pH = pK_a + \log_{10} \left(\frac{[HCO_3^-]}{[H_2CO_3]} \right)$

166 $[HCO_3^-] = [H_2CO_3] * 10^{pH-pK_{a1}}$

167 $[CO_3^{2-}] = [HCO_3^-] * 10^{pH-pK_{a2}}$

168 where, pK_{a1} is the acid dissociation constant from H_2CO_3 (= 6.35) and pK_{a2} is the basic dissociation
169 constant from HCO_3^- (=10.33). The pH considered was the one obtained measuring at the time of
170 gas sampling. pH was determined using a Thermo pH Ross semi-micro electrode. The gases were
171 always measure at 20 °C.

172 2.4.3 Biomass determination

173 Optical absorbance at 600 nm (OD600) was measured using a UV/Vis spectrophotometer
174 (Shimadzu Europa GmbH, Germany). Dry biomass concentration was measured as total
175 suspended solids according to Standard Methods for the examination of water and wastewater
176 (Baird and Bridgewater, 2017). The doubling time was calculated according to Eq. (4).

$$G = \ln(2) * \frac{t_2 - t_1}{\ln\left(\frac{i_2}{i_1}\right)}$$

177 (4) ; where G is the generation time, t_1 and t_2 , time 1 and time 2, i_1 and i_2
178 number of cells at time 1 and time 2.

179 2.5 Experimental setup

180 The experimental setup was divided in two assays (Figure 1). Test Series 1 (TS1) consisted of an
181 initial screening of the selected bacteria from genome mining to verify i) the utilization of CO₂
182 and H₂ as carbon and energy sources, and ii) their capability to produce ectoines (Figure 1). In Test
183 Series 2 (TS2), the most productive bacteria in TS1 were optimized in 1L gas-tight bioreactors
184 under different conditions (H₂/O₂ ratios, salinity) to study the effect on growth and ectoine
185 production.

186 2.5.1 Test series 1: Growth and selection

187 In TS1, 1 mL of exponentially grown cultures was inoculated in 200 mL glass bottles containing
188 100 mL of AMS supplemented with 3% NaCl. The bottles were closed using gas-tight butyl septa
189 and aluminum caps. CO₂, H₂ and air were then injected to the headspace at an initial concentration
190 of 10 CO₂: 40 H₂: 50 air (% v/v, 1 atm) with a gas blender GB4000 of 4 channels (mcq instruments,
191 Italy) connected to 3 gas lines containing H₂, CO₂ and air. The bottles were autoclaved and the
192 buffer and vitamins added (section 2.2). Cultures were incubated at 30 °C, except for *H. schlegelli*
193 that was incubated at 65 °C. Bottles were kept under orbital agitation at 200 rpm. The cultures
194 were transferred three consecutive times in AMS under an atmosphere of 10 CO₂: 40 H₂: 50 air
195 (% v/v, 1 atm) to remove any remaining carbon sources. Assays in TS1 were performed in
196 quintuplicate (for each of the tested strains). Abiotic negative controls, prepared in the same way
197 as test bottles but without addition of inoculum were also set-up. Biotic controls, prepared with

198 trypticase soy broth, were used to ensure that cells were viable at the time of inoculation. H₂ and
199 CO₂ concentration were monitored daily. For non-flocculating species (*H. schlegelii*, *H. marinus*,
200 *R. opacus*), periodically, 5 mL of liquid culture were withdrawn to determine biomass dry weight,
201 ectoine and hydroxyectoine content. This 5 mL were replaced with fresh AMS. The values
202 obtained are represented as the average ± standard deviation of the quintuplicates. For flocculating
203 species (*P. autotrophica*, *P. carboxydivorans* and *P. dioxanivorans*) a bottle from the
204 quintuplicates was sacrificed at each sampling point to measure ectoine and hydroxyectoine
205 content and biomass dry weight. Average biomass concentrations were not obtained in the
206 flocculating species. The experiments lasted until H₂ complete depletion. An extra experiment was
207 carried out to study the conversion of CO into ectoines. This experiment was developed as TS1,
208 using syngas (10 CO₂: 30 H₂: 20 CO: 40 air, % v/v, 1 atm) and 80 CO: 20 O₂ (% v/v, 1 atm) in the
209 headspace. H₂, CO and CO₂ concentration were monitored every three days (gas sampling was
210 less frequent due to the lower growth rate of the strains in CO).

211 2.5.2 Test series 2: Optimization of culture conditions

212 TS2 was performed to evaluate the influence of different environmental factors – H₂:O₂ ratio and
213 concentration of NaCl – on the production of ectoine and hydroxyectoine by the bacterial species
214 selected in TS1. Sterile batch gas-tight reactors (1.0 L) containing 190 mL of AMS were used in
215 TS2 assays.

216 Effect of salinity and H₂:O₂ ratio

217 The effect of H₂:O₂ ratio was studied using 5 different ratios of these two gases: 70:30, 60:40,
218 50:50, 40:60 and 30:70 (H₂: air, respectively) with AMS at 3% NaCl and at atmospheric pressure.
219 The effect of salinity on the production of ectoines was tested at 8 different NaCl concentrations:
220 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90 and 100 g L⁻¹. Salinity tests were performed under an atmosphere of 30:

221 70 H₂: air. Each condition was tested in triplicate. Carbonate and bicarbonate were used to maintain
222 the pH at 7.0 ± 0.3 . The batch reactors were inoculated with 10 mL of the inoculum from TS1 at
223 an initial concentration of $7.1 \pm 4.4 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$ (Note that this value corresponds to the average initial
224 concentration of the three selected strains). The headspace atmospheric pressure was maintained
225 along time adding N₂ to the headspace. Gas, biomass and ectoine and hydroxyectoine
226 concentrations were monitored daily until H₂ or oxygen depletion.

227 Bioconversion in the optimum conditions for each strain

228 The batch bioreactors were filled with 190 mL of AMS and a gas mixture of 30:10:60 H₂: CO₂:
229 air, sealed and autoclaved in quadruplicate. NaOH 3M was used to adjust the pH to initial values
230 of 6.95 ± 0.1 . Carbonate/bicarbonate buffer was omitted to monitor accurately the fixation of CO₂
231 along time. The experiment was conducted with AMS 5% NaCl for *H. schlegelii*, AMS 6% NaCl
232 for *H. marinus* and AMS 7% NaCl for *R. opacus*. The batch reactors were inoculated with a final
233 biomass concentration of $12 \pm 4.5 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$. Headspace pressure in bioreactors was maintained at 1
234 atm along time by adding air. Everyday 5 mL of AMS were withdrawn to measure ectoine,
235 hydroxyectoine, biomass and pH. This 5 mL were replaced with fresh medium resulting in a
236 dilution rate of 0.025 d^{-1} . The experiments lasted until complete H₂ depletion.

237 **3. Results and Discussion**

238 *3.1. Selection of potential chemolithoautotrophic ectoine-producing microorganisms*

239 Several halophilic microbes have the ability to grow on CO₂ and H₂, but their potential to produce
240 ectoines using these gases is unexplored. Based on literature and genomic databases, a total of
241 sixty-two species of halophilic chemolithotrophs able to grow with CO₂ as sole carbon source and

242 H₂ as the energy source were gathered (Table S1). Eleven of them were aerobic and fifty-one
243 anaerobic. Thirty six of them had their genomes available in public databases (Table S2).

244 The pathway for ectoine production involves three specific enzymes: 1-2,4-Diaminobutyric acid
245 (DABA) transaminase (EctB), DABA acetyltransferase (EctA) and ectoine synthase (EctC)
246 encoded by the *ectABC* gene cluster (Czech et al., 2019). Some organisms also present the gen
247 *ectD* that codifies for an ectoine hydroxylase (EctD), which is required to produce hydroxyectoine
248 (Czech et al., 2018). Moreover, the enzymes aspartate kinase (Ask) and aspartate-semialdehyde-
249 dehydrogenase (Asd) are necessary to produce the precursors for ectoine production. The genomic
250 screening developed to identify species that had these genes showed that eleven of the genomes
251 screened had the genes to codify the enzymes for ectoine synthesis and six for hydroxyectoine
252 synthesis (Figure 2).

253 Genomic analysis resulted in the identification of seven aerobic microorganisms with the genes to
254 produce ectoine from CO₂/H₂: *Alkalilimnicola ehrlichii*, *Hydrogenovibrio marinus*,
255 *Hydrogenibacillus schlegelii*, *Pseudonocardia autotrophica*, *Pseudonocardia carboxydivorans*,
256 *Pseudonocardia dioxanivorans* and *Rhodococcus opacus*. Genomes of these microorganisms
257 contain genes necessary to produce precursors for ectoine synthesis (aspartate kinase (*ask*) and
258 aspartate semi-aldehyde dehydrogenase (*asd*)) and genes for ectoine production (*ectA*, *ectB* and
259 *ectC*). Moreover, the species of *H. marinus*, *P. autotrophica*, *P. carboxydivorans* and *P.*
260 *dioxinivorans* and *R. opacus* can potentially accumulate hydroxyectoine because they possess the
261 gen *ectD* in their genomes.

262 On the other hand, only four anaerobic organisms; *Achromobacter ruhlandii*, *Desulfatibacillum*
263 *aliphaticivorans*, *Desulfocapsa sulfexigens* and *Methanobacterium subterraneum* had the genes
264 necessary to encode proteins for the formation of the ectoine precursor L-2,4-diaminobutyrate (*asd*

265 and *ask*) and for ectoine synthesis (*ectA*, *ectB* and *ectC*). *A. ruhlandii* also possesses the gene *ectD*
266 to hydroxylate ectoine into hydroxyectoine.

267 3.2. Experimental screening for ectoine and hydroxyectoine producers

268 In TS1, aerobic strains identified in the genomic analysis (section 3.1) as potential ectoine and
269 hydroxyectoine producers were tested in the lab for the effective capability to produce these
270 compounds from CO₂/H₂. Anaerobic microorganisms were not tested due to their lower biomass
271 yields and smaller growth rates that these organisms usually encounter (Bae et al., 2022). The
272 results of the average values obtained in the replicates are summarized in table 1. *Alkalilimnicola*
273 *ehrllichii* has been characterized as a facultative chemoautotrophic bacterium able to use different
274 electron donors for CO₂ fixation (arsenite, hydrogen, sulfide or thiosulfate) (Hoeft et al., 2007).
275 However, in this study, it did not show activity or growth on CO₂/H₂ (after three trials), despite
276 viability of the culture when grown in rich medium. Several *Pseudonocardia* species are able to
277 grow autotrophically (Grostern and Alvarez-Cohen, 2013). From those classified as halotolerant,
278 *P. autotrophica* and *P. dioxanivorans* are described as able to grow with CO₂ as the only carbon
279 source, while *P. carboxydivorans* uses carbon monoxide (CO) as a sole source of carbon and
280 energy (Park et al., 2008) and potentially CO₂ as carbon source (Grostern and Alvarez-Cohen,
281 2013). In this study, chemolithoautotrophic growth (CO₂/H₂) was detected in *P. autotrophica* and
282 *P. dioxanivorans*. On the other hand, *P. carboxydivorans* did not grow with these substrates.
283 *Pseudonocardia* species accumulated mainly hydroxyectoine when growing with 3% NaCl.
284 Ectoine was not detected during the growth of *P. dioxanivorans*; this species accumulated the
285 highest amounts of hydroxyectoine (4% of the dry biomass) of all, at the salinity range tested.
286 However, the doubling times obtained for *Pseudonocardia* species in liquid phase were very long.
287 *Pseudonocardia* spp. display a typical Actinomycete filamentous morphology with very slow

288 growth (Franco and Labeda, 2014). This genus has received attention due to the wide range of
289 valuable chemicals that it can produce, such as antibiotics and immune-modulating factors (Riahi
290 et al., 2022), however, the slow growth of *Pseudonocardia* spp. has been identified as a drawback
291 for its implementation in cell factories. Thus, the *Pseudonocardia* species (Seipke et al., 2012)
292 identified in this study were not selected for their further optimization in TS2.

293 *Hydrogenibacillus schlegelii*, *Hydrogenovibrio marinus*, and *Rhodococcus opacus* were able to
294 use CO₂ with H₂ with doubling times inferior to 24 hours (Table 1). All these species produced
295 ectoine chemolithoautotrophically with 3% NaCl (Table 1); highest product yield of ectoine was
296 obtained for *H. marinus* (3% of the dry biomass). *R. opacus* and *H. schlegelii* accumulated
297 hydroxyectoine in addition to ectoine (25% and 82% of hydroxyectoine out of the total ectoines
298 pool, respectively). Both, *R. opacus* and *H. schlegelii* have the *ectD* gene and hydroxyectoine
299 production was expected. However, the high amounts of hydroxyectoine natural production
300 detected at 3% of NaCl in *H. schlegelii* are probably related to its thermophilic nature.
301 Hydroxyectoine, in contrast to ectoine, is a good glass-forming compound as a result of the
302 stronger intermolecular H-bonds with the OH group. It displays remarkable desiccation protection
303 properties which explains its accumulation in response to elevated temperature (Tanne et al., 2014;
304 Van-Thuoc et al., 2013). Moreover, hydroxyectoine production is more prominent in minimal
305 medium, rather than in rich medium (Tao et al., 2016). Thus, according to these results, the use of
306 a thermophilic and autotrophic bacteria can be a good approach to produce hydroxyectoine as the
307 sole osmoprotectant without the use of genetically modified bacteria.

308 The strains *H. schlegelii*, *P. dioxanivorans* and *P. carboxydivorans*, according to literature, are
309 able to grow with CO as the carbon source (Grostern and Alvarez-Cohen, 2013; Krüger and Meyer,
310 1984; Park et al., 2008). Thus, the autotrophic transformation of CO into ectoines was also tested.

311 Only *H. schlegelii* produced hydroxyectoine using CO as the only substrate (1.4%), while in *P.*
312 *dioxanivorans* the production of hydroxyectoine was only detected if H₂ and CO₂ were present
313 (see supplementary material). This could be related to the slow growth of Actinomycetes or to their
314 carboxydovoric nature (Groster and Alvarez-Cohen, 2013).

315 3.3. Best environmental conditions to enhance CO₂ transformation into ectoines

316 Overall, the best performance species for the development of a production platform for ectoines
317 from CO₂ were *H. schlegelii*, *H. marinus*, and *R. opacus* due to their fast growth and their high
318 ectoines accumulation. Thus, these were the selected species to conduct TS2.

319 3.3.1 Effect of oxygen-hydrogen ratios

320 An interesting approximation is the fixation of CO₂ with H₂ at low oxygen concentrations. *H.*
321 *schlegelii* is considered an anaerobic facultative bacterium (Maker et al., 2017), while *R. opacus* is
322 able to reduce nitrate (Alvarez et al., 2019). Both of them fix CO₂ using the RubisCO enzyme,
323 although, they also possess the key genes for CO₂ fixation through the reverse TCA cycle (typical
324 of anaerobes) (Maker et al., 2017). Hence, in this assay the bacteria was exposed to different ratios
325 of oxygen and H₂, when excess of nitrate was present, to study the potential production of ectoines
326 in the absence of oxygen. The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

327 According to the stoichiometric Eq.4 (4) (Yu and Lu, 2019) to oxidize 100% of hydrogen, 50% of
328 oxygen is required.

330 In all the scenarios where there was stoichiometric oxygen limitation, hydrogen was not oxidized
331 and growth stopped. Thus, growth and the production of ectoines in the absence of oxygen was
332 discarded.

333 The content of ectoine was not affected by the absence of oxygen in the case of *H. marinus* and *R.*
334 *opacus*. Although, higher ectoine productivities were obtained in assays with more than 15% O₂
335 in the headspace. In the case of *H. schlegelii*, lower contents of hydroxyectoine were detected
336 when oxygen was not present. Although, *H. schlegelii* is a facultative anaerobe, its growth at high
337 salinity and temperature requires the production of hydroxyectoine. Ectoine can be produced in
338 the absence of oxygen, however, the EctD protein hydroxylates ectoine in a reaction dependent on
339 iron(II), molecular oxygen, and 2-oxoglutarate (Bursy et al., 2007). Thus, even if *H. schlegelii* was
340 able to oxidize H₂ anaerobically, it could not survive at high salinity and temperature in the absence
341 of oxygen since hydroxyectoine would not be produced.

342 According to these results, further tests were done with an atmosphere of 30% of H₂ and excess of
343 O₂.

344 3.3.2 Effect of salinity

345 Salinity is a requirement to promote the expression of *ect* genes (Argandoña et al., 2021). None of
346 the strains tested could grow at salinities above 8% NaCl. *R. opacus* was the only bacteria able to
347 grow at 7%, while *H. marinus* grew up to salinities of 6%, and *H. schlegelii* grew at maximum
348 salinities of 5% using CO₂ as the carbon source and H₂ as the energy source (Figure 3). *H. marinus*
349 accumulated the highest amount of ectoine among the three tested strains. With 3% NaCl, ectoine
350 production was 32.8 ± 1.8 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹, but this yield was doubled when the bacterium
351 was grown with 6% NaCl (i.e. 79.6 ± 10.5 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹). Hydroxyectoine was not
352 detected, which was expected since *H. marinus* lacks the *ectD* gene. *R. opacus* produced $18.3 \pm$
353 4.2 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 3% NaCl. As it has been observed before for other halophiles, the
354 relative abundance of hydroxyectoine increased at higher salinities (Tao et al., 2016) in *R. opacus*,
355 while keeping similar contents of ectoine. When the salinity was risen to 6% and 7% NaCl, this

356 bacterium increased the production and accumulation of hydroxyectoine to values of 12.9 ± 3.1
357 and 48.9 ± 10.3 mg hydroxyectoine g biomass⁻¹. In the case of *H. schlegelii* the main
358 osmoprotectant detected was hydroxyectoine, whose content reached values of 48.8 ± 7.3 and 56.5
359 ± 10.7 mg hydroxyectoine g biomass⁻¹ at 4 and 5% NaCl. The higher hydroxyectoine content
360 observed at high salinities is related to its superior protective effect and important protective
361 function against desiccation in comparison to its precursor ectoine (Tao et al., 2016).

362 3.4 Ectoine and hydroxyectoine linked to CO₂ depletion over time

363 A final study was carried out combining the optimum parameters from previous tests. CO₂
364 removals of 3.1, 3.4 and 3.5 g CO₂ g biomass⁻¹ were obtained for *H. schlegelii*, *H. marinus* and
365 *R. opacus*. The pH increased in all the cases from 0.16 to 0.2 units during CO₂ removal.

366 Figure 4 shows ectoine and hydroxyectoine production along time on the batch bioreactors. *H.*
367 *marinus*, although only accumulated ectoine, had the fastest growth at 6% NaCl with the shortest
368 lag phase. Ectoine production was detected on the first day with values of 72.2 ± 10.7 mg of ectoine
369 g biomass⁻¹ and reached maximum values of ~ 85 in the quadruplicates. When H₂ was depleted
370 ectoine values decreased due to metabolic shift towards the use of ectoine as energy source (Czech
371 et al. 2018). *R. opacus* had a longer lag phase when growing at 7% NaCl. Ectoine was detected for
372 the first time on day 2 and reached its maximum contents (21.2 ± 2.2 mg of ectoine g biomass⁻¹)
373 on day 4, while hydroxyectoine production was delayed in the early exponential phase and
374 increased at the expense of ectoine when the cells were in late exponential growth (52.1 ± 4.5 and
375 48.1 ± 9.0 mg of hydroxyectoine g biomass⁻¹ by day 6 and 7).

376 *H. schlegelii* was able to grow at a maximum of 5% NaCl. Ectoine content was negligible, while
377 hydroxyectoine was the main osmoprotectant detected. This osmolite was firstly detected by day
378 3 once the biomass reached contents of 30.7 ± 6.1 mg L⁻¹ and increased during exponential growth

379 when H₂ was present to maximum contents of 62.0 ± 7.9 mg of hydroxyectoine g biomass⁻¹.
380 Depending on the bacterial species, hydroxyectoine accumulation exhibits a remarkable growth
381 phase dependence, and its production is at earlier or later stages contingent upon its physiological
382 role (Tao et al., 2016). At high temperature and salinity, hydroxyectoine was more necessary to
383 maintain the cellular integrity and that is probably why it was the only osmolite detected. In fact,
384 a side study was developed to understand the role of temperature on hydroxyectoine production
385 by *H. schlegelii*. Ectoine was detected when the temperature was decreased to 55 °C, while at 65
386 and 75 °C hydroxyectoine was the only osmolite detected (see supplementary material).

387 At present, industrial production of ectoines is primarily performed with sugars or rich carbon
388 sources in the presence of very high salinities (15-20% NaCl) which reduces the product revenue.
389 New research is focusing on the development of ectoine cell factories without salt, however,
390 genetically modified organisms (GMOs) are required. Although, this aspect reduces cost, the main
391 problems encountered are: The low productivities and low stability of non-halophilic GMOs as
392 ectoine producers, and the lack of attraction that GMOs have in the cosmetic, pharmaceutical and
393 medical market. In the case of hydroxyectoine, its single production is a rare event. The majority
394 of bacteria, with the exception of some *Marinococcus* strains and *Pseudomonas stutzeri* (Schiraldi
395 et al., 2006; Seip et al., 2011), produce it as a mixture demanding even more elaborate downstream
396 processes if hydroxyectoine wants to be recovered.

397 The result of this research demonstrate for the first time the feasibility of producing ectoine with
398 CO₂ and H₂ using relatively low salt concentrations. Additionally, hydroxyectoine was produced
399 as an isolate osmolite using high temperatures and a minimum medium. In fact, the values of
400 hydroxyectoine obtained by *H. schlegelii* are in the range of the hydroxyectoine yields obtained
401 by non-GMOs consuming glucose (70-130 mg hydroxyectoine g biomass⁻¹). However, this

402 technology still faces some limitations. The ectoine contents achieved in this study, although
403 similar to those obtained with aerobic methanotrophic bacteria (75 mg g biomass⁻¹) (Cantera et al.,
404 2017), were lower than those obtained from sugars (360-540 mg g biomass⁻¹) (Becker and
405 Wittmann, 2020; Liu et al., 2021), This is likely related to the energetic constrains of
406 chemolithoautotrophy. Nevertheless, utilization of CO₂ as carbon source may bring economic and
407 sustainability-related advantages to the process. On the other hand, technological challenges, such
408 as gas-liquid mass transfer limitations, may arise when scaling-up the technology that can affect
409 maximum ectoine productivities. In this sense, engineering reactors with improved gas-liquid mass
410 transfer may be necessary for the further implementation of this technology. Another consideration
411 is that high salinity promotes corrosion of reactor materials, conducting to extra maintenance costs.
412 Strains identified in this work produce ectoine at salinities 50% lower (6% NaCl) than the currently
413 used in the industrial ectoine production from sugars, which can offer advantages.

414 **4. Conclusions:**

415 Here a proof-of-concept for the microbial production of ectoines from CO₂ was shown, with the
416 identification of several bacterial strains able to conduct this conversion. Environmental
417 parameters (e.g. salinity) affecting CO₂-to-ectoines conversion were tested and give directions for
418 further optimization. To maximize production, utilization of reactors with improved gas-liquid
419 mass transfer may be key and remain to be tested. This research will give impetus to future
420 implementation of a new biotransformation platform capable of creating value out of CO₂
421 mitigation using extremophilic autotrophs.

422 E-supplementary data

423 E-supplementary data for this work can be found in e-version of this paper online.

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556 **Figure captions:**

557 **Figure 1:** Experimental setup of this study.

558 **Figure 2:** Presence/absence of ectoine and hydroxyectoine biosynthesis genes in
559 halophilic/halotolerant chemolithoautotrophs that use H₂ as energy source. *ectC*, ectoine synthase
560 (EctC); *ectB*, DABA aminotransferase (EctB); *ectD*, ectoine hydroxylase (EctD); *ectA*,
561 diaminobutyric acid (DABA) acetyltransferase (EctA); *ectR*, MarR-type regulator (*ectR* homologs
562 are considered genes belonging to the *ectR* gene family found within 10 kb of the *ect* gene cluster);
563 *ask*, aspartate kinase (Ask); *ask_ect*, a specialized aspartate kinase (Ask); *asd*, l-aspartate-
564 semialdehyde-dehydrogenase (Asd).

565 **Figure 3:** Average intra-cellular ectoine and hydroxyectoine content at different salinities (%
566 NaCl). Black column, ectoine; dashed column, hydroxyectoine, and grey column, total ectoines.

567 **Figure 4:** Time course of the concentration of H₂ (●, black line), CO₂ (▲, grey line) and content
568 of ectoine (◆, dashed line) and hydroxyectoine (*, slashed line) during a) *H. marinus* cultivation at
569 6% NaCl, b) *R. opacus* cultivation at 7% NaCl and c) *H. schlegelii* cultivation at 5% NaCl.

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576 **Tables:**

Table 1: Average values (n=5) of the parameters measured in TS1 for each of the strains growing at 3% NaCl.

<i>Strain</i>	Doubling Time (hours)	CO₂ removal (gCO _{2(g)} g(l) ⁻¹)	Ectoine content (mgEct g ⁻¹)	Hydroxyectoine content (mgHEct g ⁻¹)
<i>Alkalilimnicola ehrlichii</i>	-	N.D.	N.D.	N.D.
<i>Hydrogenibacillus schlegelii</i>	25.7 ± 1.0	1.1 ± 0.2	4.1 ± 1.9	18.6 ± 5.6
<i>Hydrogenovibrio marinus</i>	7.9 ± 0.9	2.3 ± 0.2	26.7 ± 3.1	N.D.
<i>Pseudonocardia autotrophica</i>	242.0 ^a	0.6 ± 0.1	7.3 ± 5.8	13.4 ± 0.3
<i>Pseudonocardia carboxydivorans</i>	-	N.D	N.D	N.D
<i>Pseudonocardia dioxanivorans</i>	81.3 ^a	0.7± 0.1	N.D	41.4 ± 9.1
<i>Rhodococcus opacus</i>	15.9 ± 3.6	1.1± 0.4	17.8 ± 1.3	5.0± 2.1

577 ^aThe biomass of the replicates was measured filtering the total volume of a bottle at each time
578 point. The value was not calculated as average. N.D. Not detected.
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Table 2: Ectoine production by selected strains with varying H₂/O₂ ratios.

H ₂ /O ₂ headspace (%)	H ₂ removed (%)	Biomass (mg L ⁻¹)	Ectoine content (mg _{Ect} g ⁻¹)	Hydroxyectoine content (mg _{Hect} g ⁻¹)
<i>Hydrogenibacillus schlegelii</i>				
70/6.3	9.2	32.6 ± 2.1	2.6 ± 0.2	5.7 ± 0.7
60/8.4	15.2	64.7 ± 11.7	1.9 ± 4.6	15.3 ± 2.3
50/10.5	19.6	84.8 ± 5.9	2.5 ± 6.7	12.7 ± 2.9
40/12.6	28.1	96.9 ± 12.3	2.1 ± 1.9	19.6 ± 8.9
30/14.7	30.7	106.5 ± 8.9	0.6 ± 0.3	24.8 ± 7.6
<i>Hydrogenovibrio marinus</i>				
70/6.3	11.1	26.6 ± 5.3	33.1 ± 5.5	ND
60/8.4	12.2	44.7 ± 8.2	27.0 ± 5.0	
50/10.5	15.7	63.0 ± 0.4	32.4 ± 4.2	
40/12.6	24.7	89.3 ± 2.3	26.2 ± 2.8	
30/14.7	30.3	96.1 ± 0.5	31.9 ± 5.3	
<i>Rhodococcus opacus</i>				
70/6.3	12.8	56.6 ± 8.3	19.3 ± 3.3	6.1 ± 1.3
60/8.4	16.7	82.9 ± 24.7	17.9 ± 4.4	6.1 ± 1.5
50/10.5	24.1	87.1 ± 6.7	16.6 ± 3.4	3.6 ± 3.6
40/12.6	30.3	113.0 ± 21.1	16.7 ± 0.07	5.7 ± 1.1
30/14.7	29.8	188.9 ± 20.6	17.3 ± 3.4	5.5 ± 0.4

588 N.D. Not detected.

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601 **Figures:**

602 **Figure 1:**

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612 **Figure 2:**

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630 **Figure 4:**

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